

EXTRACTION OF HIGH VALUE PRODUCTS FROM AVOCADO WASTE BIOMASS

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ABSTRACT

This work studies the oil extraction and recovery of bioactive compounds from Brazilian and Mexican avocado seeds and peels of Hass cultivar using Soxhlet (SE) with hexane, ethanol, and ethyl acetate as solvents; and supercritical carbon dioxide (scCO₂) with ethanol and ethyl acetate as cosolvents. Also, the fatty acids (FAs) profile, total phenolic content (TPC), and antioxidant activity (AA) in avocado seeds measured. Finally, the dynamic extraction curves of scCO₂ were modeled with a multi-way partial least squares regression (MPLSR).

The highest extraction yields were observed when ethanol is used as solvent in SE (up to 14 wt%) and as cosolvent in scCO₂ (up to 6.9 wt%). TPC was higher in SFE of avocado seeds, while higher values of AA were obtained using SE. MPLSR model obtained for the scCO₂ extraction showed an average absolute deviation below 0.5 wt% for 360 measurements using only eight factors.

Keywords: Avocado; Waste biomass; Supercritical fluid extraction; Soxhlet extraction; Bioactive compounds; Multi-way partial least squares.

Abbreviations: AA antioxidant activity; ABTS 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid); AOAC Association of Official Analytical Chemists; ASE accelerated solvent extraction; BR Brazilian; CV cross-validation; DoE Design of experiments; DPPH 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl; EtOH ethanol; FA fatty acid; ME Mexican; MPLSR multi-way partial least squares regression; PRESS predicted residual error sum of squares; scCO₂ supercritical carbon dioxide; SE Soxhlet extraction; SEM standard error of the mean; SFE supercritical fluid extraction; TPC total phenolic content; TEAC Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity; UAE ultrasound-assisted extraction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous initiatives are being undertaken to reduce the amount of unrecoverable waste generated yearly across all human activities, as part of a wider strategy to shift from a linear to a circular economy. The annual total amount of agricultural waste biomass is estimated to be about 50 billion tons of oil-equivalent [1], a significant part of which fruit residues originated from the food processing industry and postharvest losses. These huge renewable resources can be collected and subsequently transformed into value-added products and energy, displacing this way fossil resources, minimizing the volume of waste ending in landfills, and increasing the economic market share of renewable-based goods and services.

Seeds and peels of avocado (*Persea americana*) fruit are important sources of waste biomass. Given its nutritional value and health benefits, avocado is one of the major tropical fruits commercialized in the world, with an estimated production of 6.3 million tonnes in 2018 (half from Central America and the Caribbean) and with the fastest production growth in the last decade among tropical fruits [2]. During the industrial processing of avocado, the seeds, peels, but also exhausted pulp are discarded as solid waste, representing 21% up to 30% in weight of the fruit depending on the cultivar [3]. As a result, substantial waste containing bioactive compounds and essential oils is produced and stays unrecovered.

The predominant chemical constituents of avocado seeds and peels depend on the cultivar and growing conditions. Typically, avocado seeds contain 43-85 wt% (dry mass) of carbohydrates (e.g., cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin), 2-4 wt% of lipids, 3-9 wt% of proteins, and 2-4 wt% of minerals. Similarly, the chemical composition of avocado peels includes carbohydrates (44-84 wt%), lipids (2-6 wt%), protein (3-8 wt%), and minerals (2-6 wt%) [4]. As for the avocado pulp, the lipid fraction accounts for about 55 wt%; carbohydrates, 32 wt%; protein, 7.5 wt%; and ash, 5.9 wt% in dry basis [5]. The relative proportion of peel, seed, and pulp in avocado varies significantly among commercial cultivars with the peel percentage ranging between 3 wt% (Choquette) and 13.5 wt% (Booth 8); seed between 10 wt% (Nabla, Pinkerton, Lorena) and 26 wt% (Zutano); and pulp between 64 wt% (Puebla)

and 80 wt% (Choquette) [6].

Carbohydrates constitute the building blocks for a wide variety of biofuels (e.g., bioethanol), fine chemicals, or biopolymers following thermochemical or biochemical transformation pathways [7]. The lipid fraction in avocado oil is characterized by high levels (above 60 wt%) of monounsaturated FAs (e.g., palmitoleic, oleic) and relatively low levels of polyunsaturated and saturated FAs (about 17 wt% or below) [8]. Bioactive substances with beneficial effects on human health, such as tocopherols, tocotrienols, phytosterols, carotenoids, and polyphenols are also present in the avocado oil. Phenolic compounds are beneficial because of their antioxidant activity (AA), having the capacity of scavenging free radicals, donating hydrogen atoms, electrons, or chelate metal cations [9,10]. In addition, the avocado pulp is rich in essential amino acids, vitamins (D, E, B6, B12, and C) and minerals (potassium, phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium) which are of high value for food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries [3,8].

Traditional methods to recover by-products of avocado peels and seeds include Soxhlet extraction (SE) and steam distillation because these are easy to operate and represent well-established technologies. Nevertheless, these methods rely on light organic solvents (e.g., hexane) and on temperature levels that contribute to the industrial emissions of volatile organic compounds and reduce the bioavailability of bioactive substances [11,12]. These disadvantages have stimulated the study of novel technologies, particularly enzyme-assisted aqueous extraction [13], cold-pressed extraction [14], microwave- and ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) [15], high hydrostatic pressure extraction [16] and supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) [12,17]. A critical review of avocado oil extraction and refining processes can be found in Satriana et al. [18].

Among the above-mentioned extraction methods, SFE with carbon dioxide as solvent (scCO₂) has gained interest and reached the commercial scale among pharmaceutical and food industries. ScCO₂ provides separation efficiency and the possibility of operating at near-ambient temperatures, thus minimizing the degradation of thermolabile compounds. The non-flammability, non-toxicity, and odorless nature of CO₂ make the scCO₂ technology attractive for the extraction of natural products

[12,19,20]. Abaide et al. [21] compared the extraction of oil from avocado pulp using scCO₂ and compressed liquefied petroleum gas. The results show higher extraction rates and lower solvent consumptions with compressed liquefied petroleum gas, although the AA of avocado oil was higher with scCO₂.

In another study [22], a two-step extraction setup for avocado oil (scCO₂ followed by scCO₂ + ethanol (EtOH) cosolvent) produced improved oil recovery values (>97 %) and higher levels of tocopherols in the oil. Cosolvents can affect the SFE in three ways, depending on the solid matrix and its affinity to the analyte (i) enhancing the solubility of supercritical fluid through analyte-modifier fluid interaction; (ii) facilitate desorption of the analyte which can be done by polar modifier molecules which interact with the matrix and compete effectively with the active site analyte in the matrix; and (iii) distort the matrix-analyte diffusion process and allow the supercritical fluid to penetrate the matrix, due to the modifier having it to swell [23]. Mostert et al. [24] studied the influence of ripeness on the oil extraction yields of destoned avocados and compared scCO₂ with hexane extraction. The results suggest that hexane permeates better the avocado than scCO₂ since the results show higher oil extraction yields. However, hexane-extracted oils have lower quality than scCO₂-extracted ones due to the relatively higher amounts of non-triglyceride substances. The extraction of phenolic substances with scCO₂ + EtOH was also characterized and simulated in Dávila et al. [25] within the context of an avocado-based biorefinery.

The objective of this work is to address the extraction of high-value products for pharmaceutical applications from avocado waste, particularly the seeds and peels, which are currently discarded during the industrial processing. Avocados of Hass cultivar originated from Mexico and Brazil were studied and two extraction processes compared: Soxhlet and scCO₂. First, samples of avocado biomass were characterized in terms of moisture, density, and porosity. Secondly, SE and scCO₂ extraction were conducted to extract the lipid fraction of avocado seeds and peels with both extraction methods compared. Hexane, EtOH, and ethyl acetate (EtOAc) were used as solvents in SE whereas only EtOH and EtOAc were evaluated as cosolvents in scCO₂ extraction. SE with hexane is

performed to assess and compare the extraction yield with scCO₂ for the Mexican and Brazilian seeds and peels. Thirdly, the influence of the main operating variables in scCO₂ extraction, such as temperature (*T*) and pressure (*P*), were examined to find conditions maximizing the extraction yield. Then, the dynamic extraction curves of scCO₂ at various conditions were modeled with a multi-way partial least squares regression (MPLSR). Finally, the properties of the extracts obtained in both extraction methods were analyzed, such as the total phenolic content (TPC), AA, and FAs profile.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section details how the avocado seeds and peels were prepared for the experiments and characterized. Subsequently, the list of chemicals and reagents used in the extractions and chemical analysis is presented followed by the description of the experimental setup and the procedures adopted for the Soxhlet and scCO₂ extraction techniques.

2.1. Sample preparation and characterization

Mexican (ME) and Brazilian (BR) avocados from the Hass cultivar were purchased on Portuguese and Brazilian local markets, respectively. The avocado seeds and peels were prepared, dried at 55 °C for 24 h in a forced-air oven, and the final moisture level of the seeds estimated using the 925.09 AOAC method [26]. Seeds and peels were crushed with a coffee and meat mill (Arbel, Brazil) for granulometry analysis using a Tyler series sieves system (Bertel, Indústria metalúrgica Ltd., Brazil). The particles used for the SE were classified in two Tyler mesh sizes, those between 28- and 35-mesh (0.42-0.60 mm); and below 35-mesh sieves (< 0.42 mm). For the scCO₂, only particles with sizes between the 28 and 35-meshes were considered because too fine particles can cause agglomeration inside the fixed bed, creating dead zones and compaction that ultimately damage the equipment [27]. Consequently, particles below 0.42 mm were only used in SE experiments for comparison. After milling and sieving, all the samples were conserved under vacuum at -18 °C.

The real density (ρ_r , in g/cm^3) was determined using pycnometer Accu Pyc II 1340 (Micromeritics, USA), measuring the real volume of the solid matrix through the variation of gas pressure in a chamber with a known volume. Helium gas was used herein because it penetrates the pores of the plant matrix without changing its properties. The apparent density (ρ_a , in g/cm^3) is based on the external volume of the biomass and was determined by inserting each sample with known mass (m_{sample} , in g) inside a graduated cylinder to find the volume (v_{sample} , in cm^3) occupied by it. Then, ρ_a is given by: $\rho_a = m_{\text{sample}}/v_{\text{sample}}$. Once ρ_r and ρ_a , have been estimated, the bed porosity, ϵ , is found by the following $\epsilon = 1 - \rho_a/\rho_r$.

2.2. Chemicals and reagents

The solvents used were of analytical grade: hexane, 99% purity (Êxodo Científica, Brazil); EtOH, 99.8% purity (Neon, Brazil); EtOAc, 99.5% purity (Neon, Brazil); and carbon dioxide, 99.5% purity in the liquid phase (White Martins Gases Industriais Ltd., Brazil). Reagents used in the chemical analysis include methanol of chromatographic grade (99.9% purity, Panreac, Spain), 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) or ABTS ($\geq 98\%$ purity, Sigma-Aldrich, USA), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl or DPPH (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), gallic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), sodium carbonate (99.9% purity, Merck, Germany), potassium persulfate (99% purity, Neon, Brazil), and 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid or Trolox.

2.3. Soxhlet extraction

The extractions were conducted following the 920.39C method of AOAC [26], using 5 g of prepared samples to 180 ml of solvent refluxed for six hours. Avocado seeds with two particle size distributions (28-35 mesh and below 35 mesh) were extracted, but for the peels, only the sizes below 35 mesh were

employed. Furthermore, the solvents hexane, EtOH, and EtOAc were used in the SE of avocado seeds, while only EtOH was used in the SE of peels.

After the extraction, the solvent was evaporated using a rotary evaporator (RV 10 digital, IKA, USA) operating at vacuum, 40 °C, and 30 rpm to recover the seed/peel oil. To ensure a complete removal of the solvent, the oil is air-dried at 60 ± 1 °C during 48 hours, the resulting sample was weighed to estimate the extraction yield (Y , in wt%), transferred into a 2 ml vial, and stored at -18 °C for posterior chemical analysis. Extraction yield Y is expressed according to the following:

$$Y = \frac{m_{extract}}{m_{sample}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where $m_{extract}$ is the mass of the dried extract (g) and m_{sample} , the mass of the initial dried seed/peel (g).

2.4. Supercritical fluid extraction with carbon dioxide

The extractions were performed in an apparatus described in detail in previous studies [28,29]. The installation has a stainless steel cylindric vessel, with 65 cm³ of volume coupled to a heating thermostatic bath (Quimis, Model Q214S2, Brazil) and a micrometric valve controlling the flow rate. A syringe-type pump controller (Teledyne ISCO 500D, USA) is used to control either the flow rate or the pressure and is maintained at 10 °C through a cooling bath to certify that the CO₂ is liquified. Therefore, a thermostatic bath (HipperQuímica, Brazil), as well as a temperature controller (NOVUS Produtos Eletrônicos Ltd., Brazil) are connected to the syringe-type pump controller and the pressure controller (WIKA, Brazil) is attached to the main extraction vessel.

The scCO₂ extractions with EtOH as cosolvent (scCO₂ + EtOH) were performed as follows. First, about 10 g of ethanol-soaked avocado seeds (Brazilian or Mexican) are placed in the vessel at different ethanol-solid matrix raw material mass ratios, hereafter denoted as MR . Second, CO₂ is injected, and the static extraction starts for a given confinement time (30 min) at pre-set T and P .

Once the static extraction is complete, the dynamic extraction starts by using compressed CO₂ at a constant flow rate of about 2.0 ml/min, a value maintained for all the extractions and controlled by a syringe-type pump at cooling temperature and pressure of the vessel. Samples with oil extracts were collected in test tubes and immediately covered, at 2.5 min (up to 25 min), 5 min (25-30 min), and 10 min (30-60 min). Afterward, the samples were air-dried to evaporate EtOH for 48 hours and conserved at -18 °C for chemical analysis.

2.4.1. Design of experiments (DoE)

The operating conditions in terms of *T*, *P*, and *MR* in the scCO₂ extraction were established using a DoE. In this work, a 2³ partial factorial experimental design with duplicates on center points was used to analyze the impact of the independent variables on the extraction yields. The variables and respectively levels are *T* (40, 60, and 80 °C); *P* (15, 20, and 25 MPa); and *MR* (1:1, 1.5:1, and 2:1). The densities of CO₂ were obtained from the NIST database [30] at the temperature of the cooling bath (10 °C) and the pressure of the system (15, 20, and 25 MPa). Table A.1 of the Supplementary Materials presents the DoE for the extraction of avocado seeds while Table A.2 shows the DoE for the peels, which amounted to a total of 36 experiments.

2.5. Chemical analysis

All samples from the SE and scCO₂ were analyzed in triplicate. Extracts (from the extractions with seeds and peels from avocado) were weighed, approximately 50 mg of each sample (depending on available mass), then 1 ml of methanol was added and the mixture vigorously shaken for 5 minutes and centrifuged (EduTec, Brazil) for 10 min at 3000 rpm. The methanol phase was removed and analyzed by spectrophotometric methods to determine the TPC and AA methods to avoid fluctuation and variability between results. All the analyses were conducted in a spectrophotometer UV-Vis

(Global Analyser, model GTA-97, Brazil).

TPC was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method according to the procedure described by Singleton et al. [31] with modifications proposed by Song et al. [32]. In this procedure, aliquots of samples from solutions (prepared as described above) solubilized in methanol (to complete the volume up to 0.5 ml) were mixed with 2.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent 0.2 M after being diluted 1:10 in distilled water, were then kept in the darkness for 3 minutes. Afterwards, 2 ml of 7.5% sodium carbonate was added to alkalize the solution originating the blue color and the mixture was incubated in the dark for 2 hours since the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent reacted in the presence of light. If after these 2 hours the mixture did not turn blue, another dilution had to be prepared and filtered in case of turbidity to avoid affecting the absorbance measurements. Finally, the absorbance was measured at 760 nm, using methanol as the blank solution and the quantitative results were calculated using a calibration curve of gallic acid and expressed as mg GAE/100g. All the analyses were made in triplicate.

Two assays were performed to estimate the AA: ABTS and DPPH. The method used for the ABTS radical cation decolorization assays was similar to Re et al. [33]. Trolox was used as an antioxidant standard. Absorbance readings were taken at 734 nm after 6 min of preparing the samples, using EtOH as the blank solution and 100 μ l of methanol mixed with 3.9 ml of the ABTS \bullet + working solution for the control and it was used after the readings of every 3 samples. The results are expressed as μ mol of Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity or TEAC per 100 g (μ mol TEAC/100 g). To find TEAC values, a response curve for standard Trolox solutions was prepared.

DPPH assays, based on the method described in Brand-Williams et al. [34], were performed to estimate the radical scavenging activity. The aliquots used consisted of 3.9 ml of a 0.06 mM DPPH \bullet methanolic solution, mixed with 100 μ l of samples methanolic solutions, previously described. The DPPH \bullet absorbance was monitored at 515 nm after being kept in the dark for 1 hour since the radical would react in the presence of light. Methanol was used as the blank solution and the DPPH \bullet

methanolic solution was used for control. The absorbance should be between 0.1 and 0.7, hence if the sample's absorbance is inferior to 0.1, another dilution had to be made (instead of using 100 μ l, use 20 μ l). The quantification was performed using a Trolox analytical curve and the results were expressed as μ mol of TEAC per 100 g (μ mol TEAC/100 g).

The samples to measure the FAs profiles were prepared according to the official method Ce 2-66 of the American Oil Chemists' Society, which converts triacylglycerol and free fatty acid of samples into fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) [35]. FAs profile of the seeds extracts from both particle sizes (the peels were not used for this assay) was analyzed using a Shimadzu gas chromatograph (GC 2010 Plus), a capillary column (SH-Rtx-Wax (Shimadzu, Japan): 30 m x 0.32 mm x 0.25 μ m), flame ionization detector (FID) and split injection mode (1:10). This assay was not performed in the peels due to the low lipidic content. The injector and detector temperatures were 240 $^{\circ}$ C and 250 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively. The oven temperature was programmed to start at 100 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes, followed by an increase up to 240 $^{\circ}$ C at a rate of 4 $^{\circ}$ C/min and maintained at this temperature for 5 minutes. The carrier gas was helium with a volumetric flow rate of 32.5 cm^3/min . FAMES were identified by comparison with retention times of the standard mixture FAMES (Supelco, MIX FAME 37, USA). The quantification of fatty acids was conducted by area normalization.

2.6. Statistical modeling of scCO_2 + EtOH extraction

The dynamic extraction curves measured at various conditions of T , P , and MR were modeled statistically with multi-way partial least squares regression (MPLSR). This technique is an extension of the partial least squares regression (PLSR) and has been applied in areas of statistical modeling, control, and diagnostics of chemical processes [36–38]. The two key reasons for using this approach in this work are as follows. First, the possibility of predicting the dynamics of extraction yields instead of only the Y value at end time given by some set of predictors. Second, potential collinearity between variables arising from conducting neither a full nor a regular design of experiments can be efficiently

handled in MPLSR. For this work, only a brief description of the technique is presented next, while the interested reader can find the theoretical and computational details elsewhere [36,39–41].

Consider a batch data consisting of $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$ runs, where each of them has $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$ measurements of variables and $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$ responses over $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ time instances throughout the batch. Consequently, a data matrix \mathbf{X} with dimensions $(I \times J)$ and a matrix of responses variables $(I \times M \times K)$ are collected. The analysis proceeds by unfolding the three-way matrix \mathbf{Y} to create a new \mathbf{Y} matrix of size $(I \times MK)$ wherein the run direction is preserved, followed by centering and scaling each column of \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} matrices [36,37]. If the batch data is time-synchronized and no information is missing, then an ordinary PLS can be readily applied.

PLS decomposes the \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} matrices into, respectively, $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{TP}^T + \mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{TQ}^T + \mathbf{F}$, with $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{XW}$ and $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{WQ}^T$. \mathbf{T} ($I \times A$) is the scores matrix where the information on how the variables relate to each other is embedded; A , the number of factors in the model; \mathbf{P} ($J \times A$) and \mathbf{Q} ($MK \times A$), the loading matrices containing the covariance of \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , respectively; \mathbf{E} ($I \times J$) and \mathbf{F} ($I \times MK$) the residual matrices expressing the deviations between observed and modeled variables \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} ; \mathbf{W} ($J \times A$), the transformed PLSR weight matrix; and \mathbf{B} ($J \times MK$), the matrix of regression coefficients of \mathbf{Y} . The number of factors A and the estimation of \mathbf{W} , \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{P} are done by iterative procedures, including the most disseminated ones: NIPALS [41] and SIMPLS [39].

The strength of MPLSR relies upon taking advantage of the covariance of the variable trajectories using the magnitude of the deviations of each variable from its mean trajectory, as well as their simultaneous and temporal correlations. Thus, data is compressed into a model retaining only the essential information about the variables change separately and with respect to one another. After estimating the matrices, cross-validation (CV) is employed to assess how accurately the predictive model obtained can perform in practice and to determine the optimal number of PLS of factors [38]. CV divides the data into subsets where, iteratively, each one is used as a validation set while the remaining data are used as a training set to fit the model. The model giving the best validation statistic

s chosen. Here, the leave-one-out CV technique was adopted and the statistic root mean of predicted residual error sum of squares (PRESS) used [42]. Finally, the number of original variables to be included in the model was set by calculating the variable importance in the projection (VIP) of each variable [40]. It measures the influence of an X -variable by calculating the fraction of the explained X -variance, weighted by the covariance between X and Y . The minimum threshold to consider the X -variable in the model was 0.8.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Chemical characterization

The results of the chemical characterization of avocado seeds and peels are summarized in Table 1. It is observed that the difference in moisture content between ME and BR avocado seeds is not significant because the former is only slightly higher (46 ± 1 wt%) than the latter (45 ± 2 wt%). It is known that moisture levels in the feedstock affect the oil extraction kinetics and yield since water interferes with the solvent penetration in the solid matrix and oil diffusion [43]. However, as Table 1 shows, differences in extraction yields and kinetics between ME and BR avocado seeds due to water moisture are not expected.

The density values were determined only for the particle size from mesh 28-35 since that size was used on both extraction methods. Both ρ_a and ρ_r of Mexican seeds show to be higher than the Brazilians, while the porosity of Brazilian seeds is higher than the Mexicans. The differences in ρ_a and ρ_r between the seeds or the peels could be associated with their oil content, as the density decreases with the increase of oil content [44]. The average porosity of BR avocado seeds measured here is close to the BR avocado pulp of Hass cultivar ($\epsilon = 0.74$) measured in Barros et al. [45], but ρ_a and ρ_r were higher than the ones reported (respectively, 0.28 g/cm^3 and 1.09 g/cm^3). As for ϵ of ME avocado seeds, it was found to be close to the porosity of BR avocado pulp of Fortuna cultivar ($\epsilon = 0.57$), but ρ_a and ρ_r were also higher than the, respectively, 0.46 g/cm^3 and 1.08 g/cm^3 reported

in Abaide et al. [21]. Regarding the avocado peels, the results are mixed since ρ_a and ϵ are similar regardless the origin, while ρ_r of Brazilian peels are higher than the Mexicans.

Table 1. Moisture, porosity, apparent and real densities of avocado seeds and peels.

Sample	Moisture/wt%	ρ_a /(g/cm ³)	ρ_r /(g/cm ³)	Porosity
Seeds[†]				
Brazilian	45 ± 2	0.35 ± 0.01	1.468 ± 0.003	0.762 ± 0.007
Mexican	46 ± 1	0.61 ± 0.01	1.502 ± 0.003	0.594 ± 0.007
Peels				
Brazilian		0.46 ± 0.01	1.326 ± 0.001	0.653 ± 0.008
Mexican		0.45 ± 0.01	1.270 ± 0.001	0.646 ± 0.008

[†] Particle sizes between 0.42 and 0.60 mm.

3.2. Soxhlet extraction

An exploratory kinetic study was first conducted on the Brazilian seeds from size < 0.42 mm, where it was observed an increase of the extraction yield up to 8.1 wt% after 2 hours and then 9.7 wt% at the end of the experiment after a total time of 8 hours (Figure S1 of the Supplementary Materials). The SE kinetic is characterized by two extraction phases: fast extraction, with an average rate of 4.05 wt%/h between the 0-2 hours; and slow extraction, with 0.27 wt%/h of average rate between the period of 2-8 hours. This occurs because initially the oil is washed out from the surface of the ground seed or peel by the solvent and as extraction progresses, the intraparticle molecular diffusion of oil in seeds or peels dominates [46,47]. After 6 hours of operation, the average rate is virtually zero, suggesting that the extraction is complete and so it was established as the extraction time for subsequent experiments.

Table 2 shows the results of SE of the ME and BR avocado seeds and peels using hexane, EtOH, and EtOAc as solvents for two particle sizes and 6 hours of extraction. EtOH was the solvent providing the higher extraction yields, generally followed by the EtOAc and hexane for both particle sizes and avocado origins. Run 6 had the highest Y value of 10.3 ± 0.3 wt% among avocado seeds,

corresponding to the extraction of BR seeds with particle sizes below 0.42 mm. Comparing the results between avocado origins, consistently higher extraction yields were observed with BR avocados, although both BR and ME avocados are of Hass cultivar. This distinction can be associated with factors, such as the composition of avocado, ripening grade, climate, soil composition, and fertilizers used [3].

Table 2. Extraction yields of avocado seeds and peels after 6 hours using SE with hexane, EtOH, and EtOAc.

Run	Solvent	T(°C) [†]	PS (mm) [*]	Extraction yield (wt%) ^{**}	Run	Solvent	T(°C) [†]	PS (mm) [*]	Extraction yield (wt%) ^{**}
Mexican seeds					Brazilian seeds				
1	Hexane	68.75	[0.60, 0.42]	2.46 ± 0.03	7	Hexane	68.75	[0.60, 0.42]	3.5 ± 0.1
2	EtOH	78.35	[0.60, 0.42]	8.2 ± 0.9	8	EtOH	78.35	[0.60, 0.42]	9.5 ± 0.2
3	EtOAc	77.05	[0.60, 0.42]	3.6 ± 0.1	9	EtOAc	77.05	[0.60, 0.42]	4.6 ± 0.2
4	Hexane	68.75	< 0.42	3.27 ± 0.02	10	Hexane	68.75	< 0.42	3.6 ± 0.1
5	EtOH	78.35	< 0.42	9.8 ± 1.9	11	EtOH	78.35	< 0.42	10.3 ± 0.3
6	EtOAc	77.05	< 0.42	3.1 ± 0.3	12	EtOAc	77.05	< 0.42	4.8 ± 0.4
Mexican peels					Brazilian peels				
37	EtOH	78.35	< 0.42	14.0 ± 0.8	38	EtOH	78.35	< 0.42	10.0 ± 0.3

* PS - particle size. ** Average and standard deviation values of three extractions.

[†] Retrieved from [30].

Concerning the seeds particle sizes, the effectiveness of all solvents improves for particles with diameters below 0.42 mm, except in ME avocado seeds using EtOAc wherein the oil extraction yield Y lowered. The extraction kinetics is faster generally in smaller particles because the path the solvent needs to travel inside the particle is shorter, thus reducing the time for maximum phytochemical content to be extracted. Particularly, the particle size influences and dominates the mass transfer kinetics, the access of solvent into the soluble compounds, diffusion rate, and extractability [27,48]. A closer look at Table 2 shows similar extraction yields in SE + EtOH of particles with smaller sizes (< 0.42mm): 9.8 ± 1.9 wt% and 10.3 ± 0.3 wt% for ME and BR avocado seeds, respectively. This suggests that the smaller the particle sizes, the smaller differences in the oil extraction yields in SE between ME and BR avocado seeds, which implies that porosity also plays an important role in SE. Finally, the relative importance of the variables solvent, the origin of avocado seeds (related with porosity), and particle size in oil yield Y with Soxhlet extraction were evaluated by performing a

predictor screening procedure with bootstrap forest partitioning. The oil yield Y was found to be mainly affected by the type of solvent, since this variable explained 86.6% of the variability in Y , whereas the origin of avocado seeds explained 9.6%, and the particle size only 3.8%.

The SE of avocado peels was conducted using only EtOH as solvent and with particles of smaller sizes because these conditions gave the highest extraction yields in the SE of avocado seeds (runs 5 and 11 of Table 2). The Y value observed for the SE of ME avocado peels was 14.0 ± 0.8 wt%, the highest value among the seeds and peels SE, whereas the Y value in the SE of BR avocado peels was similar to the corresponding seeds with EtOH. The differences in Y between peels and seeds have been reported to be associated with their inherent physical and chemical differences. Avocado peels contain lower percentages of cellulosic material and have a looser physical structure than the seeds, allowing a more efficient extraction [49]. The results in Table 2 suggest that no significant differences are in play between the BR avocado seeds and peels regardless of the particle sizes.

Figure 1 compares the average rate of extraction for both particle sizes obtained for seeds and peels in this work with similar ones available from the literature [10,50–52]. To the best of our knowledge, there are no results reported in the open literature for the SE of avocado seeds or peels using EtOAc. The extraction with EtOH was found to attain the highest yields in seeds and peels when compared with results in the literature of the extraction with hexane as a solvent for avocado seeds [10,50,51] and EtOH for avocado peels [52]. The higher extraction yields with EtOH are clearly associated with its polarity index (5.2 [53]) and boiling point (78.38 °C). According to Halim et al. [54], non-polar solvents such as hexane interact through Van der Waals forces with the longer hydrophobic chains of fatty acids and neutral lipids, thus solubilizing these classes of lipids. Polar solvents like EtOH solubilize polar lipids associated with the cell wall by breaking down the electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding between them, in addition to solubilizing non-polar molecules. The temperature has also an important role on the extraction efficiency because causes the disruption of seeds and peels cell structures, making the analytes more available for the solvent [11,29].

Figure 1. Experimental results from Soxhlet extraction vs literature for seeds and peels. The error bars used in the chart represent the standard error of the mean (SEM). Data in R0 retrieved from [52], R1–R3 retrieved from Adaramola et al. [10]; R4, Aysu et al. [50]; and R5, Dagde et al. [51].

3.3. Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction

Tests were conducted at 25 MPa and 40 °C with 0.42 to 0.60 mm BR avocado seeds to find the best cosolvent for the scCO₂, using a 1:1 ethanol-solid matrix mass ratio. Figure 2 shows, for the scCO₂ without a cosolvent, a considerably longer period of extraction (approximately 160 minutes) and a markedly slower kinetics, with a confinement time of 60 minutes and 2.1 wt% of extraction yield. When EtOAc or EtOH are added, the extraction yield and kinetics increase by the order already verified in the SE when each one was used as the solvent. Adding EtOH as cosolvent increased the extraction yield to 4.2 wt% after 60 min and decreased the scCO₂ confinement time to 30 min, enough time to CO₂ + EtOH and the solid matrix making good contact for the diffusion process to occur during the static extraction [11,55]. This has a direct impact on the operating costs because shorter periods of extraction are required to achieve similar extraction yields. This improvement is related to the degree of hydrogen bonds caused by the hydroxyl group in EtOH, which increases the analyte solubility, eases the desorption of the analytes, and the density of the mixture CO₂/EtOH relative to the CO₂ alone at same conditions of *T* and *P* [23,56].

Subsequent experiments with the BR and ME avocado seeds were conducted using only EtOH as cosolvent and following the DoE presented in Table A.1 from the Supplementary Materials. The addition of EtOH in the extraction vessel can be performed in two ways: in-line cosolvent wherein EtOH is added to the extraction vessel and the dynamic extraction occurs with a fixed percentage of EtOH by use of a pump; or static cosolvent where EtOH is mixed with the solid matrix and quickly added to the extractor. The latter technique was used in this work because it is simpler to operate the SFE equipment unit and the energy needs are lower because only one pump is required to control the flow rate of the solvent and the pressure during the dynamic extraction phase [55].

The examination of variables affecting the extraction yields and kinetics in avocado seeds and peels is crucial to elucidate operating regions of interest. Variables with impact on SFE include T , P , solvent composition and volumetric flow, physicochemical characteristics of the solid matrix, hydrodynamics of the extraction bed, and the properties of analytes. T and P at which SFE operates affect the mass transfer of the analyte and its vapor pressure, the density of the solvent, and, in turn, the intermolecular forces between the analytes and the solvent [11,57,58]. Besides T and P , the solid matrix cellular structure influences the extraction of the compounds. Part of the analytes is easily accessible to the SFE solvent on the outer surface of the ground particles or inside the cells ruptured during grinding, while the remaining material is inside intact cells and, as a result, is less available. Consequently, the easily accessible solute is extracted rapidly, while the less accessible solute is extracted following a slower kinetic regime [59,60].

Figure 2. Experiments of BR avocado seeds with scCO₂ alone and with EtOAc and EtOH cosolvents.

In this work, the impact of the main variables on the extraction of both BR and ME avocado seeds and peels was evaluated through dynamic extraction curves at 40, 60, and 80 °C of temperature; 15, 20, and 25 MPa of pressure; a *MR* of 1:1, 1.5:1, and 2:1; for particle sizes from mesh 28–35; with a constant volumetric flow rate of 2 ml/min of scCO₂. Figure 3 and Figure 4 summarize the results of the dynamic scCO₂ + EtOH extraction experiments for the avocado seeds and peels, which are discussed next.

Figure 3. Experimental $\text{scCO}_2 + \text{EtOH}$ dynamic extraction curves for BR avocado seeds with MR equal to (a) 1 (filled) and (b) 1.5 (empty-filled) and 2 (cross); and for ME avocado seeds with MR equal to (c) 1 and (d) 1.5. Markers: square, 80 °C and 25 MPa; upward triangle, 40 °C and 25 MPa; downward triangle, 40 °C and 15 MPa; star, 80 °C and 15 MPa; diamond and cross, 60 °C and 20 MPa.

Figure 4. Experimental $\text{scCO}_2 + \text{EtOH}$ dynamic extraction curves for BR avocado peels with MR equal to (a) 1 (filled), 1.5 (empty-filled), and 2 (cross); and (b) for ME avocado peels with MR equal to 1.5. Markers: square, 80 °C and 25 MPa; upward triangle, 40 °C and 25 MPa; star, 80 °C and 15 MPa; diamond and cross, 60 °C and 20 MPa.

3.3.1. *scCO₂ + EtOH extraction of avocado seeds*

Generally, it is noticeable in Figure 3 higher extraction yields in BR seeds than in ME seeds, which is associated with the higher porosity of the former (Table 1). The highest extraction yield obtained for BR avocado seeds was 6.9 wt% for *MR* 1.5:1, at 80 °C and 25 MPa (run 23), while the lowest was around 1.9 wt% for a *MR* of 1:1, 40 °C and 15 MPa (run 19). Similarly, in the *scCO₂ + EtOH* extraction of ME seeds with a *MR* of 1.5:1, the highest yield *Y* registered was 4.3 wt% at 60 °C and 20 MPa (run 22) and the lowest *Y* was approximately 1.6 wt% at *T* of 40 °C and *P* of 15 MPa (run 36).

Positive increments on either *T* and *P* tend to improve the extraction yields, although the impact is non-linear and with interaction between those variables. This is confirmed by Figure 3c and 3d where extraction yields of avocado seeds at 60 min and 15 MPa increase with *T*, but the increase is considerably higher for the *MR* of 1.5 than it is when *MR* is 1. In Figure 3a and 3b, the yields *Y* obtained were higher at 60 min, 60 °C and 20 MPa than those at temperatures of 40 °C and 80 °C, both at *P* of 15 MPa.

From the results, it is clear that *MR* was the variable with a higher impact on *Y*'s, since a markedly increase at all operating conditions of *Y* was verified when *MR* increased from 1:1 to 1.5:1. However, values of *MR* above 1.5:1 seem to had a negative impact on the extraction because *Y* decreases with *T* and *P* constant, as it can be checked in Figure 3b. For this reason, no additional experiments were conducted at EtOH-solid matrix mass ratios above 1.5:1.

3.3.2. *scCO₂ + EtOH extraction of avocado peels*

Figure 4 describes curves with an opposite trend to the avocado seeds in Figure 3, i.e., extraction yields are higher in ME peels (3.7 wt% up to 5.3 wt%) than in BR (1.5 wt% up to 3.5 wt%). The highest yield (5.3 wt%, run 41) was obtained for the ME peels at 80 °C, 25 MPa, and a *MR* of 1.5:1,

while the lowest value was 1.5 wt% (run 43) obtained for the BR peels at 40 °C, 25 MPa, and a *MR* of 1.5:1. Worth noting that the DoE performed in the scCO₂ + EtOH of avocado peels was curtailed. Consequently, some of the extraction curves result from variables interacting with themselves.

As in 3.3.1, extraction yields in Figure 4 increase with *T*, while maintaining *P* and *MR* constant. Prior works in the literature suggest an increase of the seed/peel oil solubility with *T*, particularly at *P* higher than 25-30 MPa [61–63], and a higher disintegration of the cell walls, making the analytes more available to the extraction [58]. An increase in *T* at constant *P* reduces the scCO₂ density, an effect more pronounced at pressures near the critical point (i.e., 15 MPa), contributing alone to drop the oil solubility. However, this behavior is offset by the increase in analytes vapor pressure. The trade-off between these two competing effects depends on several factors including the physicochemical properties of the analytes and solid matrix, and the operating pressure. In the literature this crossover phenomenon, i.e., the shift from a positive to a negative correlation between *T* and the analyte solubility; is common with vegetable and seeds oils [60,64]. Finally, the behavior of the solvent also changes with *T* and *P*, as is the case with EtOH whose degree of hydrogen bonding is known to decrease with *T* and *P* [65]. However, at the operating regions studied here, this change is expected to have a marginal impact on the extraction yield.

In Figure 4b, a positive correlation between yield *Y* and *P* was observed for the ME peels with *T* at 80 °C and *MR* at 1.5:1, a similar pattern to the one in Subsection 3.3.1. This is the consequence of an increase in density, strengthening the intermolecular interactions between the solvent and the analytes, thus increasing the oil solubility [64,66]. This mechanism appears to have dominated over the negative impact of using elevated *P* in our experiments, such as the reduction of the contacting area of the solvent with pores caused by the compaction of the solid matrix [12]. In addition, variable *MR* appears to have also a significant impact on extraction yields, since 2.5 wt% was registered for the BR avocado peels at *MR* of 1:1 against 3.5 wt% at *MR* of 1.5:1 at 80 °C and 25 MPa. As previously noted in Figure 3b, *MR* values above 1.5:1 were not beneficial to improve the extraction. This counterintuitive behavior can be explained by (i) the saturation of scCO₂ caused by the higher

concentrations of ethanol, forming two phases; and (ii) the hydrogen bonding between ethanol molecules, which at higher concentrations will predominate over the intermolecular bonding between the ethanol and the polar analytes, thus reducing the interactions with CO₂ [66–68].

Figure 3 and Figure 4 allow also a comparison between the extraction curves of seeds and peels at similar conditions of *T*, *P*, and *MR*. The extraction yields obtained for the ME peels and seeds were similar for all the common conditions tested, except at 80 °C, 25 MPa, and *MR* of 1.5:1. Differently, it was observed clearly higher *Y*'s for the BR seeds (5.6-6.9 wt%) than for the peels (1.5-3.5 wt%).

3.3.3. Comparison with literature

The number of works addressing the oil extraction of avocado seeds and peels in the literature is scarce. Daiuto et al. [69] report yields of 3.32 wt% and 2.18 wt% for the seeds and peels using UAE, respectively. Using the same extraction technique, Piazza et al. [52] obtained slightly higher extraction yields for avocado peels, which are 3.64 wt% and 5.48 wt% using EtOH and acetone as solvents, respectively. Improved yields of oil from avocado peels using microwave-assisted extraction were observed by Chimsook et al. [70], ranging from 3.01 wt% to 14.09 wt% with EtOH as a solvent; and 7.22-19.22 wt%, with 2-methyltetrahydrofuran. The results obtained in this work with the scCO₂ + EtOH of avocado seeds and peels suggest that this technology is competitive because extraction yields up to 7 wt% and 5 wt% could be achieved after 60 min of operation, respectively.

3.4. Total phenolic content and antioxidant activity

Here, the results from TPC and AA assays obtained for avocado seeds and peels using SE and scCO₂ are presented and discussed. TPC and AA assays were normalized into fractions in Figure 5 using the highest values recorded for each set of samples. The nominal data can be consulted in Tables C1-C3

of the Supplementary Materials.

Figure 5. TPC and AA of seeds and peels from (a) SE; (b) scCO₂ + EtOH at 80 °C, 25 MPa; (c) scCO₂ + EtOH at 60 °C, 20 MPa; (d) scCO₂ + EtOH at 40 °C, 25 MPa. The error bars indicate the SEM.

3.4.1. Soxhlet extraction

From observing Figure 5, the highest values of TPC and AA (either by radical ABTS or DPPH) among the seeds samples SE were achieved with EtOH as solvent followed by EtOAc and hexane. The ME seeds showed higher TPCs (2992 ± 82 mg GAE/100 g) than the BR seeds (1987 ± 173 mg GAE/100 g), an inverse pattern to the extraction results where higher yields were observed with BR avocado seeds than ME seeds (Figure 1). Similarly, the ME seeds achieved, in terms of AA, on both assays the highest value among all samples of avocado seeds analyzed using EtOH as solvent (46250

$\pm 1180 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$ for ABTS and $(65750 \pm 1720 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$ for DPPH). Relatively to the SE of ME and BR avocado peels, the TPC and AA were only evaluated using EtOH as the solvent. Here, the highest TPC was observed for the ME peels ($10730 \pm 569 \text{ mg GAE}/100 \text{ g}$), as well as for the AA where values of ABTS ($(111.19 \pm 5.10) \times 10^3 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$) and DPPH ($(112.81 \pm 5.54) \times 10^3 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$) assays were registered.

Comparing the results from the chemical analyses to the SE of avocado seeds and peels with EtOH, the peels of ME avocados showed significantly higher values than the respective seeds for all the analytical indicators (TPC, ABTS, and DPPH) whereas the BR avocado peels and seeds had relatively similar values. It was found that the Soxhlet extracts of avocado peels with EtOH had significant contents of phenolic compounds with high AA. This can be explained by the accumulation of phenolic compounds in the epidermis of the fruits that work as a protection against UV radiation and to certain pathogens and predators [52]. It is noticeable in Figure 5a that the recovery of polyphenols from the avocado seeds and peels of either origin is visibly affected by the affinity between those compounds and the solvent used in the extraction. Accordingly, being EtOH the solvent with the highest polarity, it has also higher affinity with the phenolic compounds (which are generally polar), thus providing extracts with the highest TPCs and AAs [11,52].

3.4.2. *scCO*₂ + EtOH extraction

A summary of the results of the TPC and AA analysis from the experiments of *scCO*₂ + EtOH extraction is presented in Figure 5b-5d. Generally, the results show that the ME seeds and peels had higher values of TPC and AA than the BR counterparts, similar to what was observed in the SE. Also, *MR* of 1.5:1 enhanced TPC and AA for all the BR and ME seeds and peels analyzed. Comparing Figure 5b and Figure 5c, minor differences are detected in TPC and AA in all samples analyzed when the conditions changed from 80 °C and 25 MPa to 60 °C and 20 MPa. However, markedly changes in TPC and AA values are observed for 40 °C and 25 MPa in Figure 5d, meaning that increasing *T*

contributed to higher TPC and AA in both assays up to 60 °C and only marginal changes at temperatures above. *T* and *P* modify the integrity of the cell wall and the cellular elements, including the polyphenols, affecting the contact between the fluid and the solid matrix. As discussed previously in Section 3.3.2., the density and solvation strength of the solvents are dependent on *T* and *P*, influencing the selectivity due to the entrainment of non-active compounds [71].

3.4.3. *Experimental vs literature*

In the literature, the TPC values found in avocado seeds using different extraction methods ranged between 250-5730 mg GAE/100 g with UAE [69,72]; a value of 8820 mg GAE/100 g [73] with refluxed extraction; 1699-6912 mg GAE/100 g with accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) [74]; and 4500-7040 mg GAE/100 g with agitation extraction [75–77]. For the avocado peels, the TPC reported was 6350 mg GAE/100 g using UAE [69]; within 2530-6790 mg GAE/100 g using agitation extraction [75–78]; and varied from 3300-17200 mg GAE/100 g using ASE [74], being the latter the highest value found in the literature. Different factors are known to influence biologically the presence of active substances in avocados including harvest time, various external factors (cultivation, storage conditions, processing, climate), and genetic context (variety, genotype) [79,80].

A comparison of AAs obtained with different extraction methods in the literature is complicated by the different analytical assays that exist to determine them. Resorting to the ABTS method, the values reported in the literature vary between 9.10×10^3 - 1.95×10^7 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for the avocado seeds and between 1.12×10^4 - 2.42×10^7 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for the peels [69,72,74–78]. The exceptional high values of AAs for both seeds and peels ($>1 \times 10^7$ $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g) were obtained with ASE [74]. The remaining values of AAs are connected to UAE and agitation extraction methods whose values are within 9.10×10^3 - 7.92×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g, which are within the intervals obtained in this work of 1.90×10^3 - 1.11×10^5 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for SE and 5.40×10^2 - 4.35×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for scCO₂. Although scCO₂ did not provided AA above 4.35×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g, values above

1×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g were achieved for most conditions studied of *T*, *P*, and *MR*.

Using the DPPH assay, the values of AA found in literature vary within 1.28×10^4 - 1.68×10^7 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for the avocado seeds and 3.80×10^3 - 2.00×10^7 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for the peels. The AA of avocado peels did not surpass the seeds using the ABTS assay, except in some experiments from [74] where again significantly high values ($>1 \times 10^7$ $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g) are observed using the ASE. Without those values, the AAs reported with the DPPH assay are within 3.80×10^3 - 9.18×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g obtained with agitation extraction methods [69,74,81–83]. This spectrum of results achieved for the avocado seeds and peels are well within the experimental data from this study, which was 2.56×10^3 - 1.13×10^5 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for SE and 1.84×10^3 - 6.75×10^4 $\mu\text{mol TEAC}/100$ g for scCO₂. Comparing with other fruits and vegetables, the avocado by-products from the present study showed higher or similar TPCs. The TPC of selected Mediterranean fruits and northern berries ranged 69-4604 mg GAE/100 g and 1190-5080 mg GAE/100 g respectively, whereas common vegetables such as beetroot and carrots ranged 40-740 mg GAE/100 g [73,74]. These results highlight the suitability of using the avocado by-products, namely, peels and seeds, as rich sources of phenolic compounds and antioxidants. Mixtures in plant extracts make it difficult to distinguish compounds and to determine the individual AAs due to their variety and complexity. Each plant contains various compounds such as vitamins, chlorophyll, and the various phenolic compounds with distinct AAs. Therefore, more tests are needed to confirm the contribution of each compound to the total antioxidant capacity.

The solubility of these antioxidants in a particular solvent is a unique feature of phytochemicals in the food matrix, which is why there is a lack of a standard procedure to determine TPC and AA. The type and polarity of the solvent influences the electron and hydrogen transfer, which are key to the determination of antioxidant capacity [80]. For scCO₂, a relationship between the AAs with *T* and *P* could not be established. The apparent random behavior may be associated with the different compounds extracted under each experimental condition, thus impacting the antioxidant potential [11,74,84]. For this reason, it was not evident a correlation between TPC and AA in all conditions of

scCO₂ and SE since AA might be attributed to the presence of non-phenolic compounds. It should be taken into consideration that different phenolic compounds may express different antioxidant activities, depending on their structure, as well as synergistic or antagonistic effects of other compounds contained in the extract. Hence, the TPC can be used to predict their AA with some degree of accuracy [74,84].

3.5. Fatty acids profile

The composition of FAs in extracts of avocado seeds was analyzed by gas chromatography for both SE and scCO₂ + EtOH extraction and the numerical results are presented in detail in Table D1 of the Supplementary Materials. Because the FAs profiles were found to be very similar among the different solvents used in SE and between the operating conditions in the scCO₂ + EtOH, only the average profiles of FAs in avocado seeds for both extraction methods are represented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Average FA profile of the seeds (a) SE with particle sizes below 0.42 mm and (b) scCO₂ + EtOH extraction. The error bars indicate the SEM.

The main FAs found with the SE of avocado seeds were linoleic acid (44.7-47.6%) and oleic acid (30.7-36.0%), regardless the solvent used. Only a total of five FAs were identified in the extracts of SE: palmitic, oleic, erucic, linoleic, and linolenic acids. Erucic acid was only identified in samples of ME avocado seeds when the solvent EtOAc was used, meaning a particular affinity between the pair

which hexane or EtOH did not exhibit. The percentage of palmitic acid observed in the samples was within 15.4-19.3%, the linolenic acid, 3.5-6.1%; and the erucic acid approximately 2.9%. In addition, neither the FAs profiles nor the total percentage of FAs varied with the solvents used.

Figure 6b shows that only four FAs were detected in the samples of scCO₂ + EtOH of avocado seeds: palmitic, oleic, linoleic, and linolenic acids. After analyzing the samples, no notable changes were noted between samples obtained at different operating conditions (check Table D1 of the Supplementary Materials) and the principal FAs found continued to be the linoleic acid (44.0-45.0%) and oleic acid (30.2-32.9%), followed by the palmitic acid (16.4-19.6%) and linolenic acid (5.2-6.7%). Figure 6 demonstrates also that there are no significant differences between the FAs profiles of samples obtained from Soxhlet and scCO₂ + EtOH extraction methods.

Finally, we found the concentrations of palmitic and linolenic acids in FAs profiles obtained here to be within the ranges reported in the literature, which are 17.0-24.9% and 4.1-13.3%, respectively. As for the oleic acid, the range of concentrations measured in this work was well above those observed in prior works (14.9-18.6%), while the concentrations of linoleic acid are at the upper value of the interval (26.4-49.4%) reported in the literature [85–90]. These data retrieved from literature are mainly from the SE of different parts of avocado with various geographic origins. To the best of our knowledge, FAs profiles from scCO₂ extraction of avocado seeds and peels had not been previously reported.

3.6. Results of MPLSR of scCO₂ + EtOH extraction

The data represented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 were here modeled. From each batch, were taken 13 time instances in the interval 2.5-50 min. Because extraction yield is invariant and known at $t = 0$ min, this instance was not considered, as well as time instances above 50 minutes since data was incomplete and the dynamics of extraction in that region is practically null. All the data obtained in the scCO₂ + EtOH extraction for BR and ME avocado seeds and peels were considered altogether in

MPLSR. The porosity (hereafter, PY) is assumed to be the main characteristic distinguishing the origin and parts of the avocados. Accordingly, the variables or predictors considered for the X matrix in MPLSR were PY , MR , T , P , in addition to their squares and cross products. As the Y matrix, it consists of columns with extraction yields measured for each time instance and on rows of batch runs. The total number of runs I is 30, the number of X-variables J is 14, M is one, time instances K is 13, and, in turn, dimensions of matrix X are (30×14) and of Y is (30×13) . The MPLSR was carried out using JMP [42] and SIMPLS [41] algorithm with the leave-one-out CV.

The first MPLSR analysis of the $scCO_2 + EtOH$ extraction of avocado seeds gave a minimum root mean PRESS after CV of 0.78 and the minimizing A was 4. These four PLS factors can explain 99% of the X-variance and 58% of the Y-variance ($Q^2 = 0.40$). It is noticeable in the percent variation explained for Y-variables plot (Figure 7a) a lower prediction capacity of Y1 (Y predictions at 2.5 min for all runs) by the PLS model. A similar result is verified when A increases from 4 to 14 ($A = J$) to which explained Y-variance is $R^2 = 0.82$ ($Q^2 = 0.33$), while Y1-variance is approximately $R^2 = 0.65$. Contributing to this difference is the higher interference of other factors such as the morphology of the solid matrix and the mass transfer in the initial stages of the experiment occurring essentially at the surface of the solid material. Therefore, Y1 was excluded from the following regression.

After removing Y1, a second MPLSR was performed where the variance of Y-variables explained by the four factors improved slightly ($R^2 = 0.60$, $Q^2 = 0.42$), but now the R^2 is within 0.82 and 0.85 for all the responses when $A = J = 14$. The VIP of each original variable, with $A = 4$, was computed and the results are summarized in Figure 7b. Twelve of the 14 original X-variables were identified as statistically important in describing the variation of Y, from which the cross products $T*MR$, $PY*T$, and $PY*MR$ were the ones with higher impact. These results confirm the observations made in Section 3.3 wherein variable MR has an appreciable impact on the extraction yield dynamic curves, although its effect appears coupled with T and PY . Predictors $PY*MR$, PY , and PY are those capturing the impact in Y by changing from Brazilian to Mexican avocados and seeds to peels. Contrarily, it also reveals a minor impact of variable pressure in estimating Y since P-containing predictors were

among the ones with the lowest VIP. For the final analysis, the predictors P and P^2 were excluded since their VIP was below the threshold.

Figure 7c and Figure 7d summarize the results from CV with a reduced X-variables matrix and the predictions vs experimental values of Y . The minimum root mean PRESS after CV is 0.75 obtained with $A = 8$. In general, a good agreement is verified since the model with only eight factors is capable of explaining about 99% of the variance in X-variables and 77% of the variance in Y-variables ($R^2 = 0.77$, $Q^2 = 0.43$) for a total number of 360 measurements. All the 12 original variables have VIP values above the threshold and their importance in descending order is $T*MR > PY*T > PY*MR > PY > PY^2 > MR^2 > PY*P > T*P > P*MR > MR > T > T^2$. Thus, MR and PY containing predictors continue to be the most important in explaining the variance in Y-variables.

The predicted and experimental $scCO_2 + EtOH$ dynamic extraction curves for ME and BR avocado seeds and peels are shown in Figure 8. The average absolute deviation of the predictions is 0.48 wt%, meaning that the MPLSR model is a valuable tool to predict the dynamics of SFE in BR and ME avocado seeds and peels as a function of temperature, pressure, and EtOH-solid matrix mass ratio.

Figure 7. Results of the MPLSR for the scCO₂ + EtOH extraction wherein (a) is the plot of explained Y-variance in the first analysis with four factors; (b) the VIP of predictors in the second analysis; (c) PRESS vs. number of factors in CV, and (d) the residual plot obtained with 8 factors.

4. Conclusions

This work addressed the extraction of oil and bioactive compounds of waste avocado seeds and peels of Hass cultivar originated from Brazil and Mexico. The physicochemical properties of solid samples were classified by particle size and characterized in terms of moisture, density, and porosity. ME seeds revealed moisture levels (46 wt%) similar to the BR seeds (45 wt%), while apparent and real density measurements of ME seeds were higher (ρ_a , 0.61 g/cm³; and ρ_r , 1.502 g/cm³) than the BR seeds (ρ_a , 0.35 g/cm³; and ρ_r , 1.468 g/cm³). As to the avocado peels, narrow differences in the densities between the avocado origins were noted. Two extraction methods were studied and their performance compared: SE using hexane, ethanol, and ethyl acetate as solvents; and SFE with carbon dioxide as solvent (scCO₂) and ethanol and ethyl acetate as cosolvents.

Figure 8. Predicted (line + marker) and experimental (marker) scCO₂ + EtOH dynamic extraction curves for seeds (solid line) and peels (dashed line) of (a) BR and (b) ME avocados. Filled, $MR = 1$; empty-filled, $MR = 1.5$; and cross, $MR = 2$. Markers: square, 80 °C and 25 MPa; upward triangle, 40 °C and 25 MPa; downward triangle, 40°C and 15 MPa; star, 80 °C and 15 MPa; diamond and cross, 60°C and 20 MPa.

The present study demonstrated that it is possible to extract oil using SE with yields up to 10.3 wt% for avocado seeds (BR, < 0.42 mm) and 14.0 wt% for avocado peels (ME, < 0.42 mm). Regarding the scCO₂, the highest oil extraction yields achieved were 6.9 wt% for the BR avocado seeds at 80 °C and 25 MPa with a mass ratio of 1.5:1 and 5.3 wt% for the ME avocado peels obtained at similar operating conditions. These values corresponded to solid matrices with particle sizes from mesh 28-35 (0.42 to 0.60 mm). The comparison between solvents concluded that EtOH was the solvent and cosolvent providing the best extraction results in both SE and scCO₂, respectively. EtOH-solid matrix mass ratio, temperature, and pressure were the major variables evaluated in scCO₂ + EtOH where higher extraction yields were observed at higher values of T and P .

The TPC analysis showed that ME seeds had higher phenolic content than BR seeds, both for SE + EtOH (2992 ± 82 mg GAE/100 g) and for scCO₂ + EtOH (5136 ± 12 mg GAE/100 g using 1.5:1 mass ratio at 80 °C and 25 MPa). ME peels also revealed higher TPC than BR peels both in the SE + EtOH (10730 ± 569 mg GAE/100 g) and in scCO₂ + EtOH (4668 ± 112 mg GAE/100 g using 1.5:1 mass ratio at 80 °C and 25 MPa). To measure the AA of the extracted oil from avocado seeds and peels of both origins, ABTS and DPPH assays were performed. The results of both assays revealed higher AAs in extracts from ME seeds and peels than from the corresponding BR seeds and peels,

independently the extraction method used. The highest AA measured by DPPH assay in extracts from ME seeds using the SE + EtOH was $65750 \pm 1720 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$ and using the scCO₂ + EtOH at ethanol-solid matrix mass ratio of 1.5:1, 80 °C, and 15 MPa was $59970 \pm 9720 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$. As for the extracts from ME peels, the highest AA measured by DPPH assay using the SE + EtOH was $(112.81 \pm 5.54) \times 10^3 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$ and using the scCO₂ + EtOH at ethanol-solid matrix mass ratio of 1.5:1, 80 °C, and 25 MPa was $(47.23 \pm 5.09) \times 10^3 \mu\text{mol TEAC}/100 \text{ g}$.

The FA profiles were determined only for the avocado seeds. Either for SE and scCO₂ extraction, both ME and BR seeds showed similar profiles but the Mexican resulted in the highest ratio between unsaturated and saturated fatty acids, both for SE + EtOH (5.49, size < 0.42 mm) and scCO₂ + EtOH (5.33, using for 1:1 mass ratio at 60 °C and 20 MPa). The main FAs found in the avocado seeds were linoleic acid and oleic acid, independently of the extraction method or origin.

When comparing extraction methods, generally higher extraction yields were found with SE than with scCO₂ extraction. The higher yields of SE are justified by the longer extraction times and larger amount of solvent used, leading to higher energy and material consumptions. Also, SE requires higher temperatures of operation to reduce the surface tension and viscosity of the solvent, improving its solubilization and increasing the number of the compounds soluble in the solvent phase. These factors turn the scCO₂ extraction into a more advantageous option from economic and environmental viewpoints offsetting the higher capital costs. However, a fair comparison between scCO₂ extraction and SE can only be performed by optimizing the operating conditions accounting the economic and environmental criteria using a systematic approach. In this context, mathematical models capable of predicting the performance of process units depending on the operating conditions can be extremely valuable. This is the case of the MPLSR model obtained for the scCO₂ + EtOH in Section 3.6, which showed to be able in capturing adequately the dynamics of extraction at different conditions of temperature, pressure, and EtOH-solid matrix mass ratio.

In this study, it was important to obtain substances with high AA through an efficient extraction

process to turn waste into a “high value-added” product. It was found that the ME avocados had more potential in terms of the quality of valuable compounds in them than the BR avocados. Differences between the results given by different types of seeds or peels can be assigned to factors such as harvest time, external factors (cultivation, storage conditions, processing, climate), and genetic context (variety, genotype).

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